

i+1 IMPLEMENTATION: A LANGUAGE ACADEMY CASE STUDY

Renato P. Yu Jr, LPT, MAEd¹, Princess De C. Puntual, LPT, MAEd²,
Carly Mae J. Suico, LPT, MAEd³

¹*Ministry of Education, Murcia, Spain*

²*Al Rawabi Private School, Jeblat Hebshi, Bahrain*

³*University of Cebu – METC, Cebu City, Cebu, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

Language teaching becomes effective when the input is comprehensible enough with the learners. This study analyzed teachers' i+1 implementation along lesson preparation, teaching-learning activities, and assessment in one language academy in Cebu. This study used the descriptive case study approach to investigate and describe how Comprehensible Input is reflected and accomplished in the academy. Based on the result of the 4-point Likert scale survey, the language teachers have fully understood the nature of i+1. In fact, its actual implementation in the classroom varies from one teacher to the other. There are also recurrent themes in each area under the i+1 implementation based on the teachers' attestation. Writing down the lessons and preparing instructional materials are the common practices teachers do before the class starts when preparing a lesson while in the actual teaching-learning process, they make use of video clips and visual arts to supplement the lessons and do collaborative learning to allow students maximize the use of the English language. Lastly, pen- and-paper test and output-based assessment are done to keep track of the students' understanding of the lessons. Overall, the teachers in the academy implement common practices of a Comprehensible classroom – the lessons are all a level higher from the students' current level. However, teachers have to be consistent in teaching integrating i+1. From the results of the three least level in the Likert scale, interview session, and teachers' implementation, this study shares recommendations to attain an in- depth understanding of what Comprehensible Input is and how it is practiced in an English classroom.

Keywords: *assessment, comprehensible input, i+1, implementation, lesson exemplars, preparation, teaching-learning activities, training matrix*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers' understanding how humans acquire and make use of languages can be beneficial in teaching second language learners – especially English language learners. With that, it becomes a duty of teachers to ensure that students acquire the target language rather than just learning it. During instruction, there is an emphasis on the message's text rather than its format. Language teachers need to focus more on the communicative facet of the language instead of focusing solely on sentence patterns and rules for the students to memorize.

As what Krashen (1988) said, meaningful contact in the target language and real communication is essential for acquisition, in which speakers are more interested in the ideas they are conveying and comprehending than the form of their utterances. Stephen Krashen's Second Language Acquisition theory offers five hypotheses about how language acquisition occurs. Among those hypotheses, this paper is solely focused on the input hypothesis that describes how learners acquire a second language. Based on this hypothesis, when the target language 'input' is received by students whose 'input' learned in the class is a stage higher than one's current linguistic competence, he or she progresses. When a person receives a second language input that is beyond their current level of competence, they are expected to develop further. As an example, if a learner is at stage 'i', acquisition arises when he is exposed to 'Comprehensible Input'.

For the reason that not many students are in the same level of language proficiency concurrently, Krashen proposed that an intrinsic communication input is the way in creating a syllabus, ensuring that each learner receives some 'i+1' input appropriate for one's current stage of linguistic competence. Although the learner is exposed to a one level higher, it is still expected that the lessons are comprehensible enough. With the concept of 'i+1', this can be employed to second language learners, especially those who want to learn English, as it becomes dominant in the world.

According to Krashen, in SLA, the Input Hypothesis is essential for language learning, since L2 acquisition is dependent on understandable input (Zhang, 2009). In the classroom, for example, learners get intelligible input from teachers, whose primary responsibility is to support language learners through this input. When learners' language production, which is characterized as 'output,' is improved and monitored when negotiation happens in any language input (Pérez-Vidal, 2017). The only way to get linguistic information from 'input' to 'output' is to interact with it. Learners choose to take in 'portions of understandable material and choose correct language form to express themselves', according to Krashen. This procedure allows students to internalize what they have learned and experienced' (Zhang 2009, p.93).

Furthermore, according to Akan (2018), Krashen's (2009) hypothesis of acquisition through comprehensible input "demands meaningful contact in the target language -

natural communication - in which individuals are more concerned with the messages they are expressing and comprehending than with the structure of their utterances." (p.120). Because comprehensible input is so important in SLA, it may be viewed as a set of methods.

In Wu (2010) study, "The Application of Input Hypothesis to the Teaching of Listening and Speaking of College English," found various issues in teaching listening and speaking of college English, including unsatisfactory teaching materials and ineffective learners. With these issues in mind, the author developed some solutions for teaching the two language skills holistically. Wu (2010) concluded that when the Input Hypothesis is applied to the teaching of College English listening and speaking, learners will benefit more; "comprehensible input" can pique their interest in the listening materials, causing them to want to listen more which leads to the acquisition of some language and cultural background and related information beyond the language they will acquire; and the input's effectiveness will facilitate more successful output; and the input's effectiveness will facilitate more successful output.

One of the English academies in Cebu is a language academy which was established in 2013, primarily applies Comprehensible Input compared with other language schools and centers. In this academy, students' program takes a notch higher than the result of their placement or leveling test. When the students' overall level falls under A2 level, an elementary level, the program given to them is intermediate, B1 level. In this way, language students will be given challenging tasks, but not too difficult for them to accomplish.

The actual application of $i+1$ in an English classroom has not yet been clarified and this becomes an important issue to be addressed in this study. With this, there is the matter whether the teachers are following the right way in applying the Comprehensible Input. There is also the concern on its proper application especially the appropriate activities in teaching the lessons. In addition, the language teachers in the Academy did not have an in-depth orientation and workshop on how this 'i+1' concept works in the teaching-learning process. This is when the problem comes in, which this study wanted to raise and address.

Therefore, it was deemed necessary to conduct this study on $i+1$ in the academy. The purpose of this research is to further explore the Comprehensible Input, $i+1$, in teaching English as a Second Language (ESL) in the language academy in terms of the teachers' understanding of $i+1$, teachers' actual implementation from lesson preparation, teaching-learning activities to the assessment through their narratives and document analysis, and lastly the suitable course of action to improve the utilization of $i+1$ in the teaching of English to foreign students.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the implementation of $i+1$ in teaching English as a second language in a language academy in Cebu.

Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What are the teachers' level of understanding of $i+1$;

2. How does 'i+1' being implemented along with
 - 2.1 lesson preparation
 - 2.2 teaching- learning activities,
 - 2.3 assessment?
3. What are some relevant proposals based on the findings of this study?

METHODOLOGY

This study made use of mixed method approach for the presentation of results which aimed to have an in-depth analysis and description of the implementation of Comprehensible Input in the English programs in the language academy. Furthermore, the core design of this paper is descriptive case study. This design was utilized to analyze both quantitative and qualitative data, then merged the two sets of results to see how the i+1 implementation results converge and diverge.

Particularly, this study used case study because it needed to have a concrete and in-depth understanding on how English teachers apply i+1 in their classes. Furthermore, it would be beneficial to find out if this Comprehensible Input by Krashen works in the real world, in such, the context of teaching English to second language learners. This would also allow the teachers in the academy to explore i+1's meaning, characteristics, and implications in the teaching- learning process. Indeed, this case is predominantly distinctive as the language academy's branding is teaching a level higher from the students' current level as compared with other language academies.

RESULTS

Teachers' level of understanding

Table 1 summarizes the statements about the extent of language teachers' understanding level in i+1. Specifically, it is divided into three tables: full understanding, moderate understanding, and no understanding. This table also provides the level of understanding in every statement of the survey based on the weighted mean.

Table 1
Teachers' Level of Understanding in i+1

Statements no.	Weighted Mean	Level of Understanding
1-5	4.0	Fully Understood
6-10	4.0	Fully Understood
11-15	4.0	Fully Understood
16-18	2.5	Moderately Understood
19-21	2.5	Moderately Understood
22-23	2.75	Moderately Understood
Overall Weighted Mean	3.30	Fully Understood

DISCUSSION

Based on this summary in Table 1, it shows that among the 23 statements in the survey, 15 of which are considered as fully understood by the language teachers, that is equivalent to 65.22%. While the rest of the principles, it was only moderately understood. Meaning, the level of understanding of the teachers in i+1 or Comprehensible input is that they fully understand the concept with an overall weighted mean of 3.30. Regardless of the teachers' overall level of understanding, it states that there are still concepts about i+1 that the language teachers may not have a full understanding about.

One of the characteristics of Comprehensible Input that the teachers have a full understanding about is that there are appropriate materials and activities in each proficiency level such as presenting pictures when introducing new words instead of

translating to the students' native language. This is supported by Echevarría et al. (2000) that in order to make content comprehensible for English language learners, there must be a contextualization of key vocabulary. This is achieved through examining the material and make a list of key terms that are necessary for grasping the lesson's main topics. According to the authors, teachers could also introduce and define words clearly and concretely, demonstrate how they are used in context, and explain how to integrate synonyms to convey meaning. In addition, the teacher must take into account the text's complexity as well the students' linguistic competency when choosing material for reading for an extended session. (Namaziandost and Ahmadi 2019). This is not only for reading but also for the rest of the skills that the students need to learn.

Language Academy's teachers understand that beginning learners require more explicit teaching and language acquisition in order to establish a solid foundation in the new language. That is why the students' level should always be taken into consideration. According to Echevarria, et al. (2017) in their book "Making Content Comprehensible for English Learners: The SIOP Model", there are 3 features of CI: appropriacy of speech; clarity of academic tasks, and diverse ESL techniques used. This only explains that everything transpires in the classroom should be comprehensible for the students for the students to achieve every task.

On the other hand, teachers have a moderate understanding in terms of language production and specific activities. Since Comprehensible Input is a concept in Second Language Acquisition, it is expected that language production cannot be taught directly, but rather acquired. For the acquisition to occur, students need to be immersed with the target language. The more the learners are exposed to the target language, and the more time students spend using academic language, the faster language proficiency will be established (Echevarría & Graves, 2010; Saunders & Goldenberg, 2010). In order for the learners to be exposed, appropriate activities should be given to them. Though teachers are aware that there are appropriate activities for each level, they moderately understand that a common technique that can be applied in the class is circling or using repetitive questions to elicit student output (Gaab, 2014; Roberts, 2006).

Teachers should completely emphasize the value of selecting input that is relevant and appealing to students while employing Comprehensible Input (CI). When students are presented with the ability to observe what they are being taught, their learning becomes situated rather than abstract (Echevarria, Vogt, & Short, 2000). This means that whatever is being taught in the class, teachers should see to it that it is applicable in students' real-life situations. Finally, when students get to the intermediate level, more input and less specific grammatical instruction should be provided. In a conventional grammar teaching, students are taught the structures individually with sample sentences, but with comprehensible input, activities are more emphasized for them to acquire it naturally. Others may have students act out pieces of a story, make certain sounds or actions when targeted structures appear, or incorporate other activities which get students engaged in hearing, seeing, and producing with the target language (Cheatham et al., 2013).

From the interview, teachers have shared the same idea about it that, Comprehensible Input/ $i+1$ is teaching a level higher from the student's current level. An

example given by *Teacher 1*, when a student is in B1, they have to use a B2 material for them to reach that level at the end of the program. As supported by *Teacher 3*, she shared that the materials should not be too easy nor too difficult to understand. Comprehensible input mainly focuses on the students acquiring a second language. Additionally, it is specified as the knowledge one receives (input) that should be somewhat greater than or equal to what one can create independently, as demonstrated in *i+1* (Abukhattala, 2013).

From the teachers' answers, it can be proven that they are correct about what comprehensible input is based on Krashen's description. All these can be substantiated when they noted that,

"...if student is in B1 level, we have to teach them, uh I mean we have to apply and use materials for a higher level like the B2 level so that those students from B1, who are currently in B1 as they enrolled to our, to our academy we may have to make sure that after the program the duration of the program they will now be on B2." (T1).

"...the student's level is A2, of course I had to use the b1-b1 material of course, is of course my materials, uh. Of course, the task, uh, the task that I gave to my students of course is also b1. Though the student's level is actually A2..." (T2)

"...the perspective of the *i+1* method is that students can-can advance from their levels or can learn more, can acquire the language if the-if the materials or the methods are not too easy for them and not too difficult that they could no longer grasp. So, in terms of comprehension, it has to be something that is a little bit, um, a little bit um comprehension-friendly, which means that they can understand it but at the same time, it is something that they, it is also something that something where they could learn a lot from it too. It's not just, it's not too easy for them to just settle on this material and not learn anything anymore but it has to be a material where they could understand it." (T3)

"...it must go through a level of assessment before we actually try, before we actually implement it and *i+1* is about second language learning or it's mainly focused on people who want to learn the language as, or, English as their second language, not their first one." (T4)

It then can be implied that teachers understand the basic idea of comprehensible input, its relation to acquisition, production of the target language, appropriate activities and lessons, and how it is reflected in the classroom. This may be because the teachers have already been teaching in the academy for quite some time and already understood the fundamental ideas of Comprehensible Input, *i+1*. In addition, teachers may have already researched about this and thus made them aware of it. Although, there are still parts that the language teachers need to understand more and should have an in-depth understanding of. As can be examined in the table, some teachers have answered 1 and 2, which means that there are areas that they still do not understand and/or partially understand. With this, it should be taken into consideration that regardless of the overall results, the individual response of the teachers should also be raised and addressed.

i+1 Implementation

A. Lesson Planning

Before a program starts, the language academy requires its teachers to prepare a Summary of Learning Session (SLS) which shows the topics that will be discussed in the whole duration of the program. It can be observed that i+1 is implemented in the SLS as it contains lessons and sometimes activities that are a level higher from the student's current level. These lessons were taken from CEFR where teachers could extract lessons. Aside from the SLS, the prepared lesson material such as the PowerPoint presentation clearly showed how interactive and contextualized it was based on the student's background. To support this, according to the book titled Making content comprehensible for English learners: the SIOP Model by Echevarría et al. (2017), created to make content material understandable to English language learners, an effective Sheltered Instruction Observation Protocol (SIOP) instruction involves the utilization of a variety of additional resources to complement and contextualize the core curriculum. This explains that when planning for the classes, teachers should consider a variety of additional materials that can contextualize the lessons relevant to the students, textbooks or online materials.

Writing down the lessons

Lesson plans may not be required to be submitted and checked in the academy; however, teachers still make a draft on their class flow for them to be guided. In their personal lesson plan, teachers write down the objectives of the lessons and the expected outcome or performance from the student. The planning stage of the lesson is reflected when Teacher 1 explained,

"I do make my lesson plans. I, it's actually the most fun part for me, I really like planning; So um there was really no clear reference on how to make a program or a lesson plan under a CEFR standard, so what I have to do is that I pick up the book and then I quickly, not quickly, but I really read uh the lessons and the materials that are there and then I have to make a lesson plan on or sometimes I just really follow like uh, I just really follow the flow for example in the book." (T1)

Similarly, when preparing a lesson plan, Teacher 2 mentioned,

"I have to create my lesson plan. Yeah, so because without lesson plan, so your, the flow of your teaching is quite messy. Okay so first, I plan it, yeah and then with objectives, the materials that I have to use, of course, the activities for the students so yeah and in my activities, I had to-I had to find the other activities which couldn't be found in my book as well because if you always rely to the book, of course the students could check it already. of course. The students could check and um the activities will not be exciting because they already know what activities are. So, what I, what I did is, I made my own activities. So of course, my resources were the internet, yes, specifically the Cambridge, okay yeah, of course. In planning with my activities, I have, I had also the check on the lev- on the level of that activities if this activity is intended for b1 or yeah or this activity is intended for b2 so like that." (T2)

Considering that the teachers in the academy are not required to make lesson plans, Teacher 3 added about the making of Summary of Learning Sessions and/or Summary of Activities, she stated,

“I have SLS, we do SLS in the academy or in this case, sometimes we also do SOA - summary of activities, so um that's for the SLS, it's more summary of learning sessions that's the SLS. If it's group classes, we usually have to plan at least a month or weeks before, weeks after we learn what sort of, what sort of, the sort of level these students have. Then, um if most of these students are from b1, so we have to think oh maybe we can give them b2 lessons and then we deliberate not just me as a teacher, one teacher, but you know like as a team of teachers. We deliberate which-which types of lessons, which types of classes, I mean lessons, activities that we can do, that we need to do with them um for individuals to, for individual classes.” (T3)

As what was being said, teachers have the freedom to make their lesson plans just to make their class go smoothly. Some may also choose to write down points that should happen in the class to achieve the objectives, or they can follow the conventional way of writing it. With this, Teacher 4 mentioned that,

“if it's a group class, yes. I write but um just points, but if individual, I try to make it more like of a flow, like flowy, because I try to look at what the individual person's needs are and then I try to go to that, to that part during um, I try to shift to that part during class, so it's like, it's like looking at more, looking more on a personalized lesson if it's individual and if it's in group. I would like to um just at least write what I would do but um sometimes, my objectives are like just one, just let them understand the lesson and then have the output, it's always the output for me.” (T4)

Preparing Instructional Materials

In terms of choosing materials for the classes, teachers in the academy have similar experiences. They have different sources to enrich the lessons and to make sure that the materials used are level-appropriate for the students. In addition, teachers made sure to maximize the academic books provided in the academy intended for each proficiency level. These books become the bases in terms of content and activities. To attest this, the language teachers shared that,

“...what I have to do is that I pick up the book and then I quickly, not quickly, but I really read uh the lessons and the materials that are there and then I have to make a lesson plan on or sometimes I just really follow like uh, I just really follow the flow for example in the book in this uh the book that we use uh there's this part that we have to do a warm-up activity.” (T1)

“I had to use the b1-b1 material of course, is of course my materials uh of course the task uh the task that I gave to my students of course is also b1.” (T2)

“I really consult books. I first and foremost, I check out all of my materials come from books that tell you, these are advanced books good for c1-c1- c1, c2 or these are books that are good for um intermediate level students.” (T3)

“we had like um a library of materials ready. I work on that sometimes. I don't edit it and sometimes I do.” (T4)

In some situations, teachers also made use of reliable internet sources to check for more activities and lesson content. They shared that there are sources that indicate the level of the topic for them to keep aligned on the students' program and language level. Language teachers specifically mentioned that,

“also from the internet which is not-not the internet in general. But I look into the website for CEFR on their website. Yes, they give, they have actually, they have a website, so I go to their, they have pdfs, they have books they have materials, so until now I'm still studying it.” (T1)

“so of course, on-on the internet, so you can find a lot of activities there and also every activity has its level. Yeah, so that's-that's my other resources aside from the book that um I use.” (T2)

“in vocabulary lessons, I try to use uh the Cambridge dictionary, because uh yesterday, I asked my-my colleagues what-what dictionary did they use, because if you notice, the Cambridge dictionary has like an indicator if it's a b1 word, a b2 word and it really helps a lot when you're trying to prepare a lesson and to be, to be careful of such words that you use.” (T4)

A part of lesson preparation are the materials that would be used in the class. These materials should be comprehensible enough for the students to understand its content. In fact, understanding the linguistic input is the most basic technique for a learner to acquire a language. As a result, the clarity of the educational materials is crucial. For example, if the subject is too simple to comprehend, the students will gain nothing. On the other hand, if the material is complex for the students to comprehend, they will never gain a clue. As a result, an ideal set of teaching materials should include sufficient comprehensibility. In this part of the study, the teachers' instructional materials were assessed through the recorded classes. Since all of the teachers used PowerPoint and other materials in teaching, these things were intensely observed.

Based on the gathered and observed materials, the teachers have similarities and differences, although the lessons were all the same for all levels. Three teachers generally made their materials comprehensible for the students that they had. However, there was a teacher who used some materials that were too difficult for the students' level like the choice of words in the PowerPoint. Regardless of this, that teacher made sure to clearly explain each part for the students to understand. That is why, it is important to use appropriate words based on the students' language level. It should not be too difficult for them to understand as well as not too easy. Oversimplification of written and spoken language restricts exposure to a wide range of sentence structures and linguistic structures. (Crossley, et.al., 2007). On one hand, when presenting multimedia technology understandable, most of the teachers did this most of the time. One teacher must insert videos or audios to enrich the comprehensibility of her lessons.

In four qualities of a comprehensible material, teachers were divided. They were divided specifically when presenting visuals for beginners, introducing motivational

activities such as games, integrating different language skills, engaging students through authentic materials, and making them valuable to the students. It is vital that when teaching beginners to present relevant images for the abstract ideas to be concretized. This is supported by Short et. al. (2012), that visual representations, not just language-based explanations, provide students with needed, additional support. Furthermore, these materials should be authentic and incorporate different language skills to engage and motivate students. In fact, instructional materials become even more comprehensible when these provide practicality to the students' lives.

Finally, the teachers in the academy were observed to apply uniformly with their materials. They constructed their PowerPoint and other educational materials relevant, making the students' language and culture regarded and supported. As a matter of fact, teachers contextualized all the materials from the students' place of origin to their individual field of study. In contrast, the learning materials should be consistently constructed, analyzed, and improved and show continuity in every class session. Supplementary materials are also recommended that teachers could use to make their classes more engaging. These materials and resources such as pictures, realia, and multimedia are used to create context and reinforce content concepts (Echevarria, Vogt, & Short, 2000). Though teachers at times reviewed the previous lesson to introduce a new one, it would be better if there is a connection from one topic to another to fully make the materials comprehensible. There was also a lack of accessibility of learning tools for the students' further study.

In lesson planning, language teachers should assess the comprehensibility of the materials, activities, and assessment. Echevarría et al. (2000) in their book *Making content comprehensible for English language learners: the SIOP model*, the authors mentioned what needs to be included in making lesson preparation comprehensible, which includes: clearly defined content objectives, specifically stated linguistic aims; content suitability; utilization of supplementary materials; content adaptation to all proficiency levels; and relevant activities that integrate concepts with real-life situations. Students become more engaged as a result of these preparations because they grasp the teachings, regardless of whether they are at a higher level than their current language proficiency.

B. Teaching-learning activities

During the class observation, it was clearly observed that teachers applied *i+1*. Some teachers clearly explained the academic tasks by modeling them on how to do various tasks. These tasks were challenging yet comprehensible enough for the students to achieve. In addition, teachers made use of different input sources by exposing students to the four language skills. For those teachers who were handling students in the lower level, they maximized the use of visuals to show the meaning of words. In discussing every lesson, teachers explained it by giving examples. It was also observed that teachers connected the lessons on the students' field of study, something that they could relate to. In terms of vocabulary, regardless of having the same topics, teachers made sure to only introduce words that are not too difficult for the students to understand. Videos, like TED Talks, were also part of the classes which the students needed to give reaction to and express their thoughts in English. Games and interactive activities also made the classes comprehensible. Students learn English lessons by naturally engaging with the

activities. In fact, error analysis was observable by letting the students correct the mistakes in sentences based on the lesson being discussed. Feedback was also apparent during the class to let the students identify the parts that they still need to work on and improve.

Amplifying Learning through Video Clips and Visual Arts

Teachers in the academy had similar and different strategies in delivering the lessons. One of the strategies that they used was using videos or clips to concretize the abstract lessons and make it more comprehensible to the students. Krashen (1982) states that an instructor may help students learn by giving them suitable comprehensible input. This means that teachers can use materials to further explain and deliver the lesson to make it comprehensible. The videos could also serve to pique students' interest especially at the start of the class. From the video, they talk about it and the teacher asks relevant questions to check students' understanding that would lead to the main lesson for the day. To prove these scenarios, teachers pointed out that,

“so sometimes, I uh I pick up ted talks or short clips from the internet to show what this abstract concept is and then I will ask them questions, what do you think it was showing? and then I lead them to that theme.” (T1)

“I presented to the student was um a video about something which is related to feelings and emotions I showed a video. Then after I showed the video, I asked the students um how did the character feel, yeah, in the video, of course. The student had to respond about what she thought about the feeling of the character, then right after that, of course I had to ask the students also about her feeling while watching the video. Then after that, I had, after that, I also presented some useful expressions and phrases which is related to feelings and emotions.” (T2)

“I show them videos, movie clips to introduce lessons. For-for beginner students, I usually show them pictures.” (T3)

“I try to make it visual like everything visual especially if it's a younger learner, so it's-it's that hard and um basically, I just pick up the lessons that I, that I will teach and then make a PowerPoint of it and then yeah, never forgetting the-the classic um motivation part of-of the class and then discussion.” (T4)

Language teachers could learn more various activities to keep the students excited every day in class. When students are naturally acquiring, the faster the acquisition of the language happens. Some Comprehensible Input (CI) activities in the classroom may include vocabulary introduction with pictures as opposed to translation, total physical response storytelling (TPR-S) to introduce vocabulary and syntax structures, describing images with target structures, movie/film talks, and video input in the target language (Borich, 2017; Crouse, 2014; Ponniah, 2010).

Collaborative learning

Most of the teachers apply collaborative work or activities in their classes for the students to share their ideas and be able to each other when someone needs help. An example for this is through small group discussion where students are collaborates with each other

and ask students questions that require long answers. To prove the statements, teachers stated that,

“So, I question them a lot or that and then I do collaborative learning with them so it doesn't feel like they are the only one learning; so feeling alone while learning.” (T1)

“Sometimes I plan activities that are good for a week especially if I teach writing classes where we do collaborative-collaborative editing in class where we do collaborative planning in class, collaborative correcting in class, something like that.” (T3)

“I really like um writing activities and small group discussions, and like um- um like question and answer but not really the trivia kind but the, but the- the ones that's like, how do you call it long-long answer questions; that questions that would elicit long answers individually um and activities like games.” (T4)

Overall, it can be examined that there are only few things that the teachers in the language academy need to work on in terms of their class flow. It is best for them to consistently apply the areas that make the lessons comprehensible for the students. With this, teachers are expected to be aware of what transpires in their classes when implementing Comprehensible Input.

c. Assessment

When conducting comprehension check, conducting group discussions, and making the assessment comprehensible, most of the teachers were able to show it. They gave short quizzes after each discussion and tasks for the students to exhibit their understanding. Also, the students were given chances to something on what they think about based on the lesson discussed. From these observations, there is a dynamic assessment which is a more contemporary idea that connects assessment and instruction through interaction and cooperation between learners and teachers, with the goal of "understanding individuals' skills and fostering their growth." (Poehner, 2009: 471) in an integrated way.

All language teachers showed consistency when providing assessment to the students in terms of making it drawn from the content, real-life situations can be applied, and its criteria or rubric is both comprehensible and task specific. Through these strategies in giving assessments, students would be able to realize the objectives of the activities and perform based on what they are expected to do. In contrast, all teachers should improve on giving different types of tests, a good amount of output, and variety of drills and practices. When students are offered with a variety of tests, the teachers could assess and evaluate comprehensively the extent of their understanding. Furthermore, a reasonable number of outputs like drills and practices can encourage and motivate the students to demonstrate their skills applying the lessons being learned. The more activities they receive, the more opportunities for them to use the target language in diverse situations.

However, most of them also needs to work on formative assessment and making other tasks both challenging and instructive. Through comprehension check in the class, it could improve teachers' practices especially when students do not understand the

lessons or commit repeated errors. This only means that they need more input that is comprehensible. The tasks given to the students should also be challenging because if it is too easy for them, they will not gain anything, and if it is too difficult, then the task would not be completed. It should be in the level that the students learn something more from the assessment. An effective approach especially in assessing students' understanding is through Assessment for Learning (Afl). AfL is a good way to assess students' understanding and where they are in their learning process, and it has been found to have additional advantages, such as offering chances for feedback and raising teaching and learning standards (Black & William, 2009).

Pen-and-paper Test

In order to monitor students' understanding of the lessons discussed, it is important to carry out tests like formative and summative tests. This is also a way to assess the comprehensibility of the lessons. From the class observation, it clearly supported what the teachers mentioned during the interview. As what teachers mentioned that,

"...summative tests, so we have to make our own summative tests." (T1)

"I give them quizzes or test, I give them quizzes um twice a week, yeah twice a week, yes so only twice a week not every day. So, before I end my class, I give them a particular quiz, a particular quiz and also that's based on the lesson that we had, it should be related and um if this activity that is written in the book, of course, I sometimes, I don't follow that." (T2)

"I basically just construct it according to, if I do quizzes, it's about the discussion. If it's just a formative assessment, it's about what I discussed." (T3)

This same goes with other teachers who provide quizzes by making one or search on the internet to modify based on the lesson's content. To verify this explanation, the teachers explained that,

"so if it's like a major quiz or let's say an exam, I make them on my own. I try to make it, um, by myself as possible, because of authenticity and um I also learn as I make it. But if it's like a normal quiz day, I tend to search online and then um I try to edit it and then I try to look at their examples in mind, so I try to work on that." (T4)

"a particular quiz and also that's based on the lesson that we had, it should be related and um if this activity that is written in the book, of course, I sometimes, I don't follow that. Sometimes, I modify or when I check on the internet, I also don't follow what uh what it is written there, of course. I had to modify as well if I have a lot of time." (T2,)

A teacher also shared that apart from providing summative test, she also investigates if her lessons, and activities still coincide with the students' language level through proficiency test. As what teacher 3 stated,

"I do not just do a summative test wherein I just, I just find out we do that of course in the academy, but I see to it that I do periodical proficiency tests so that I could see to it if I'm still teaching appropriate level, appropriate lessons, and activities." (T3)

Output-based Assessment

Aside from the pen-and-paper test, a student-centric way to achieve the objectives of the lessons is through an output or a specific outcome. This is an innovative way to check students' way of showing their understanding of the lesson; a product of what has been learned. During the interview, one teacher specifically mentioned that her way of conducting formative test is by letting a student perform a discernable output. To support this, the teacher made mention that,

"I usually end my class uh depending on which skill was the last skill that I taught them, so usually uh it could be the output skills which is the reading or the writing, ay no, the writing and the speaking so I do like uh like an activity which makes the student feel more comfortable; and if it's a speaking activity then, uh, I try to like make uh make an activity for them to speak to be able to speak publicly or and-and because and because it's just a one-on-one mostly, so it's just me and the student." (T1)

This also same goes with another teacher who gives out performance-based activities depending on the language skill. As what teacher 4 specifically stated that,

"so if it's summative exams, I tend to give-I tend to give out instructions on um output-based performance tasks, like um it can be reporting or um speech or in writing they should-should write." (T4)

Assessment in a comprehensible classroom is important especially when teachers use different ways to check students' knowledge. It is recommended that teachers do not stick on traditional forms of assessment, but rather focus on outcome-based assessment. Teachers should be aware what the students already understand and the areas or lessons that they still need to improve on for supplementary lesson and activities. From time to time, comprehension check is a good strategy to monitor students' progress. This way, teachers can evaluate his strategy in teaching the lesson more comprehensible for the students to understand.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that there is a gap between teachers' understanding in i+1 and their actual implementation of it. In terms of knowledge, which was measured through the Likert scale, teachers have a full understanding in i+1. In addition, they also shared the nature of Comprehensible input/i+1 during the interview. However, during their teaching-learning process, from the recorded class observation, the language teachers showed inconsistencies in terms of giving more speaking time to the students, providing various assessment techniques, and the comprehensibility of lessons. Furthermore, some activities were not that engaging that would spark students' interests especially grammar lessons. Nevertheless, the language teachers were able to link the lessons and the students' lives making it practical and relevant. Students, on the other hand, were given opportunities to express their ideas using the target language. Lastly, the use of pictures, multimedia, and concrete examples during the class also helped the students enrich their learning.

Recommendations

From the findings revealed and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are presented:

1. A seminar-workshop is recommended for the teachers to have an in-depth understanding of the nature of i+1. This is also an avenue for them to identify activities and effective practices in a comprehensible classroom.
2. Daily or weekly lesson plans could be prepared by the teachers for them to be guided on the lesson flow in every class. In addition, a head teacher may be assigned to check the lesson plans and materials of the teachers to make sure that it is level appropriate.
3. Weekly or monthly class observation by a head teacher may be done to assess the implementation of i+1 and to keep track of the teachers' teaching practices. Seminar- workshops could be done especially to newly hired teachers who are new to Comprehensible input/i+1.
4. Language teachers may use a variety of drills and practices for the students to experiment with the target language. Furthermore, assessment tools should be varied to check students' learning and understanding. Lastly, letting the students do group activities and interact with Filipinos may be done to practice their skills in a real-life situation.
5. Future researchers may conduct studies about Comprehensible Input related on:
 - a. Challenges in Implementing Comprehensible Input in an English Classroom
 - b. Input Hypothesis vs Output Hypothesis: A Comparative Analysis
Students' lived experiences in a Comprehensible Classroom: A Phenomenological Study
 - c. Comprehensible Input in a Philippine Public-School Setting
 - d. Effectiveness of Comprehensible Input in teaching English to beginner level
 - e. English learning, teaching, and assessment: A Comprehensible Input Approach

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this research, there were some considerations that needed to be followed for the protection of the people involved in the study. These research ethics were monitored by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) before the research could start. The researchers made sure that before the start of the interview and survey, letters of permission and consent were sent to the academy, Coordinator and Co- coordinator, and the participants. The consent explained the methods that ensured the four participants received adequate treatment and were protected from danger, privacy, as well as recognizing their individual autonomy and rights. In fact, it was also indicated that the participants and the academy would gain benefits directly as the results and the recommendations were presented to furtherly revamp the implementation of comprehensible input (i+1).

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